

STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING VOCATIONAL TEACHER COMPETENCIES IN THE 21ST CENTURY IN VOCATIONAL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS UPPER NORTHEASTERN REGION 1

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ABSTRACT

The objectives of this research were to 1) study the problem of necessary competencies vocational teacher competencies in the 21st century. of Vocational Educational Institutions in the Upper Northeastern Region 1, and 2) create a strategy for developing the necessary competencies of Vocational Educational Institutions in the Upper Northeastern Region 1. Mixed qualitative and quantitative research. Phase 1 studies the problem of necessary competencies vocational teacher competencies in the 21st century. of Vocational Educational Institutions in the Upper Northeastern Region 1, Uses research The target group was 15 experts, and the sample group was determined to be 353 people, research tools include semi-structured interviews and questionnaires, analyzing the content data and using statistics, frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation—phase 2 to create a strategy for developing used by organizing a workshop. Target groups include 18 experts and 30 experts, confirming the development strategy's suitability and feasibility. The research tools were suitability and feasibility assessment forms. To analyze data using statistics, frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Research results.

The problem of necessary competencies and determine strategies for developing vocational teacher competencies in the 21st century. of Vocational Educational Institutions in the Upper Northeastern Region 1. found that 1) Ethics and Code of Ethics for the Teaching Profession 2) Teamwork, 3) good service, 4) self-development, and 5) focusing on results in work. Competencies in line of work include 1) curriculum administration and learning management 2) synthetic analysis and research for student development, 3) classroom management, 4) building relationships and cooperation with communities for learning management, 5) student development, and 6) leadership and the results after undertaking a confirmation strategy suggested that both overall value higher than 3.51 which is considered acceptable based on the assessment criteria that have been established.

Keywords: Necessary Competencies Vocational Teacher, Strategy for Developing the Necessary Competencies, Institutions in The Upper Northeastern Region 1

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I. INTRODUCTION

Part of His Majesty King Bhumibol Adulyadej's royal advice on education on June 11, 2012 reads: "Teachers are no less important than students. One problem is a lack of teachers because the number is not enough and teachers move frequently. Therefore, before selecting children Teachers should be developed first. Be ready to teach children to get the desired results. Therefore, teachers must be selected and developed. Teachers' social status must be set appropriately. and instilling awareness using the philosophy of Sufficiency Economy" which leads to the first chapter in the development of the nation's teachers. This marks the starting point of studying the problems and needs of educational development in all dimensions that respond to changes in the 21st century, leading to ideas for developing the teaching profession in various areas. From the discussion of the Subcommittee on Vocational Education In the Senate Education Committee to listen to perspectives on problems and opinions from producers, users, and those involved with vocational education teachers, it was found that Thailand's vocational and technological education management system is still unable to produce and develop vocational education teachers. Can have quality This is due to many reasons, such as the shortage of technician teachers. Bachelor's degree operations technologist and skilled industrial technicians and technicians in some professional fields (Commissioner's Office 3 , 2017)

From the research report of Opas Sukwan, he studied the teaching competencies of vocational teachers in Bangkok. Measure the competency of vocational education teachers using a scale. Teacher competency: It was found that the teacher competency of vocational education teachers These include: 1) Developing a curriculum and teaching and learning for vocational teachers that promotes the development of professional competencies. Experiences are organized during study. and professional practice, and 2) development of regular teachers to strengthen the competency of vocational teachers according to the needs of the vocational teacher group. And competency development is used in a variety of ways. Therefore, vocational teachers should have professional competence to always be ready to disseminate knowledge according to the needs of technological developments in the industrial world. The guidelines for developing professional competencies of vocational teachers in the century 21 is a guideline for preparing professional teachers for vocational education in the future. (Opas Sukwan , 2019) Also from the research report of Rajamangala University of Technology Thanyaburi.

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About professional standards for teachers in vocational education The results of the research show that the teaching professional standards set by the Teachers Council are It is highly inappropriate for vocational teachers who must teach theory in the classroom. and must teach in a laboratory with expensive and easily dangerous equipment to students And at some levels, vocational teachers must teach in the workplace. Therefore, it is recommended that there be standards or guidelines that are specifically appropriate for vocational teachers. In addition, vocational teachers also have theoretical knowledge. You must also have knowledge of testing machines and equipment related to production.

Teachers must therefore have high skills and caution. and are meticulous in caring for their students, therefore it is appropriate for vocational teachers to receive professional licenses that are different from other types of teachers. Therefore, the Office of Competency Development for Teachers and Vocational Education Personnel It is a government agency under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission. Efforts have been made to develop Vocational education teacher competencies and guidelines for driving the development of vocational education teachers From the summary of human resources management results for the year 2022, the number of educational institutions is 433, with 13,855 vocational teachers and the summary number of students for the academic year 2023 is 647,875 people. It can be seen that there is a ratio of 1 teacher to 47 students, which is 1: 47. But the criteria set by the Office of the Teacher Civil Service and Educational Personnel Commission for the number of teachers to the number of students is 1:30, which is much higher than the set criteria. (Office of Education Region 10, 2023)

Vocational teachers under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission In the Upper Northeastern Province Group 1 , it consists of 5 provinces: Udon Thani, Loei, Nong Bua Lamphu, Nong Khai, Bueng Kan, totaling 3,014 people. In the 2022 academic year, it was found that there were 1,370 vocational teachers in Udon Thani Province, 508 people in Loei Province , 313 people in Nong Bua Lamphu Province, 544 people in Nong Khai Province , and Bueng Kan, 279 people, with the highest number of teachers in Udon Thani province and teachers in Bueng Kan Province are the fewest, which Uthumporn Intachak said that future vocational teachers must give their full potential and be consistent with the competencies of each person. Including the mechanism for developing vocational teachers, it is necessary to rely on driving spatial education. Cooperation partners are the key to success and promoting the development of innovations and diverse curricula to promote work skills (Uthumporn Intachak , 2019).

From the information mentioned above The researcher therefore sees the importance of developing the competency of vocational teachers in the 21st century at Vocational Educational Institutions in the Upper Northeastern Region 1 as a guideline for creating new strategies for the Office of Teacher Competency Development and Vocational Education Personnel. Government agency under the Office of the Vocational Education Commission and the Office of the Teacher Civil Service Commission and Educational Personnel It is a central personnel management organization for government teachers and educational personnel. Including the Teachers Council.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THIS STUDY

1. To study the problem conditions and necessary competencies of vocational teachers in the 21st century in upper northeastern vocational education institutions 1.
2. To create a strategy for developing vocational teacher competencies in the 21st century in vocational education institutions in the upper Northeastern Region 1.

III. DELIMITATION OF THIS STUDY

The key informants are experts in providing vocational teachers in the 21st century in upper northeastern vocational education institutions 1. Data collection method for qualitative research of 15 people including vocational teachers of the Upper Northeastern Vocational Educational Institute 1 who are experts with at least 6 years of teaching experience by selecting a specific type. 2) Vocational teacher civil servants of Vocational Educational Institutions, Upper Northeastern Region 1.

The research instrument used a structured interview. How to collect data in quantitative research and the sample group was determined to be 353 people and distributed questionnaires.

IV. METHOD IN THIS STUDY

It is a mixed research method using both qualitative and quantitative research methods carried out in 2 phases as follows:

Phase 1 research studies various problem conditions. In the field of vocational education, the dual system Northeastern Vocational Education Institute 1 is a variety of research (Mix Method Research). There are 2 steps as follows:

Step 1 study the problem conditions and necessary competencies of vocational teachers in the 21st century in upper northeastern vocational education institutions 1. Qualitative research The target group is 15 vocational teachers of the Upper Northeastern Vocational Educational Institute 1 who are experts with at least 6 years of teaching experience by selecting a specific type . The research instrument used was a semi-structured interview form. It has content regarding 5 core competencies: 1) Focusing on performance results 2) Good service 3) Self-improvement 4) Teamwork and 5) Ethics and Code of Conduct for Teachers and competency in 6 operational areas including 1) Curriculum administration and learning management 2) Student development 3) Classroom management 4) Analysis, synthesis and research for student development 5) Leadership and 6) building relationships and cooperation with the community data collection, The researcher coordinates with experts to schedule an interview and analyze the data by synthesizing the content and summarizing.

Step 2 study the problem conditions and necessary competencies of vocational teachers in the 21st century in upper northeastern vocational education institutions 1. conducting quantitative research. The population research was Vocational teacher civil servants of Vocational Educational Institutions, Upper Northeastern Region 1, number 3 , 014 people (Office of the Vocational Education Commission , 2565) Sample group used Yamane formula with a confidence level of 95 percent and an error of 5 percent resulted in a sample of 353 people (Yamane, 1973) using a simple random sampling method were obtained. The tool used in the research was a questionnaire. 2 episodes as follows: Part 1: General information of the respondents. Part 2 : Questionnaire to study the competencies required of vocational teachers in the 21st century at Vocational Educational Institutions in the Upper Northeastern Region 1 , consisting of 5 main competencies : 1) focusing on results of work performance 2) good service 3) personal development, 4) teamwork, and 5) teacher ethics and code of conduct. and competencies in 6 operational areas , namely 1) curriculum management and learning management, 2) student development, 3) classroom management, 4) analysis, synthesis, and research for student development, 5) leadership, and 6) building relationships. Research tools: the researcher used a questionnaire created by the researcher himself by using data from literature studies that document concepts and theories; It is a 5-level estimation, divided into 3 parts, part 1 asks for basic information about the respondents. It is a checklist by asking about gender, age, education level, part 2 asked about the problem of organizing dual vocational education system. Bachelor's degree Northeastern Vocational Education Institute 1. It is a 5-level rating scale according to the Likert Method (Boonchom Srisaard, 2010) as follows:

Level 5 represents the highest level of problem.

Level 4 means a high level of problem

Level 3 means the level of problem is moderate.

Level 2 means less problem level.

Level 1 represents the lowest level of problem.

Statistics based on data analysis are the percentage, mean, and standard deviation in the discussion of results; to describe the results obtained from a scale questionnaire. Estimated values considering the average score level according to 5 criteria (Boonchom Srisaat, 2010).

A questionnaire was drafted and used as a research tool and consult with the advisor. The revised tool was then brought to the experts to check content validity and the language used (wording) and finally, scores from all 5 experts were taken to find the correspondence index between the items of each question with the purpose to be measured (Index of Item – Objective Congruence: IOC). This was achieved by using the formula of Rovinelli and Hambleton referred to in Boonchom Srisaat, (2010). The questionnaire's IOC value was 0.80-1.00. The questions were considered consistent with the content. The modified tool was later tested with a sample of 30 people to find the alpha coefficient (Alpha-coefficient) of the whole questionnaire using Cronbach's method (1970) (Cronbach), a value was 0.980. The method of data collection - The researcher distributed questionnaires, collected the data, and verified the completeness of the data in the questionnaire manually along with the questionnaire to interpret the results is the code according to the manual by entering the prepared code, saving, and processing. The data analysis obtained from closed-ended questionnaires and used as statistics mean analysis which was applied from Boonchom Srisaard (2010) as follows:

Level 5 with a mean value between 4.51–5.00 means the highest level.

Level 4 with a mean value between 3.51–4.50 means a high level.

Level 3 with a mean value between 2.51–3.50 means moderate.

Level 2 with a mean value between 1.51-2.50 means low level

Level 1 with a mean value between 1.00-1.50 means the lowest level.

Statistics based on data analysis are the percentage (Percentage), mean (Mean), and Standard Deviation (Standard Division: S.D.) in the discussion of results; (Class Interval) to describe the results obtained from a scale questionnaire. Estimated values considering the average score level according to 5 criteria (Boonchom Srisaat, 2010).

Phase 2: To determine the strategy for developing vocational teacher competencies in the 21st century in upper northeastern vocational education institutions 1. The research is divided into 2 steps as follows:

Step 1: Determine the draft strategy for developing vocational teacher competencies in the 21st century in upper northeastern vocational education institutions 1, using the SWOT technique. Target groups are experts with knowledge and experience regarding the development of vocational teacher competencies in the 21st century at Vocational Educational Institutions in the Upper Northeastern Region 1, including 1) strategy experts, 2) educational institution administration experts, and 3) Teaching experts, 18 people, choosing a specific method by organizing a workshop. Research Instruments, the researcher prepared audio recordings, attended observations, participated in activities by presenting strategic drafts to meetings, and prepared data records and recorded images while organizing activities. Data Collection, Collected by taking meeting notes, recording audio, and recording images. Data analysis, used content analysis to quantify the frequency of the data and summarize the overall picture of the content in the manner of discriminating, categorizing, and finding relationships the results of the study will lead to the conclusion of issues that are important variables.

Step 2: Evaluate the development strategy for developing vocational teacher competencies in the 21st century in upper northeastern vocational education institutions 1, conducting quantitative research. Target groups were experts with knowledge and experience, divided into 2 groups: 1) a group of 5 development strategy experts and 2) a group of experts with knowledge and experience regarding the development of vocational teacher competencies in the 21st century. Upper Northeastern Vocational Educational Institution 1, 29 people, by purposive selection, totaling 34 people, choosing a specific method (Purposive Sampling) by organizing a workshop.

Research instruments The researcher used an assessment form to assess the suitability, and feasibility of the strategy as a scale to perform scoring according to the criteria that determined the scores of the 5 weight ranges as follows: Level 5 means the assessment is at the highest level

Level 4 means the assessment is at a high level

Level 3 means the assessment is at a moderate level

Level 2 means the assessment is at a low level

Level 1 means the lowest rating

Data Collection 1) The researcher coordinated with the sample group to inform the objectives and benefits of the research and requested permission to collect data; 2) The researcher collected the data by calling the appointment in advance and then taking the assessment together with a request for cooperation; and 3) The researcher traveled to collect data by himself. Data analysis by content analysis and synthesis content then a descriptive overview was summarized and data analysis the researcher analyzed the data by using a ready-made program that analyzed frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. The results were interpreted according to the following analytical criteria (Boonchom Srisaat, 2010).

Level 5 with a mean value between 4.51-5.00 suitability and feasibility is at the highest level.

Level 4 with a mean value between 3.51-4.50 suitability and feasibility is at a high level.

Level 3 with a mean value between 2.51-3.50 suitability and feasibility is at a moderate level.

Level 2 with a mean value between 1.51-2.50 suitability and feasibility is at a low level.

Level 1 with a mean value between 1.00-1.50 suitability and feasibility is at the lowest level.

The researcher has set the criteria that for the assessment to pass, the assessment must have a means of no less than 3.51 to be considered the evaluation is passed criteria.

V. CONCLUSION

From the research on Strategy for developing the necessary competencies of Vocational Educational Institutions in the Upper Northeastern Region 1. The results of the research were summarized as follows:

Phase 1 The results of the study of problem conditions and necessary competencies of vocational teachers in the 21st century at vocational education institutions in the upper Northeastern Region 1. 1. The qualitative research results by interviewing 15 people. Found that 1) Most of them are female, accounting for 53.33 percent, aged between 45–54 years, accounting for 53.33 percent, master's degree level, accounting for , 80.00 percent and marital status, accounting for 60 percent, 2) Results of interviews with experts and opinions regarding problems in conditions and necessary competencies of vocational teachers in the 21st century at vocational education institutions in the upper Northeastern Region 1. Found that Problems, core competencies Including Competency 1: focusing on results in work, including, vocational teachers are complex in their work and dealing with the bureaucracy. This may cause problem-solving to be disorganized and not as effective as it should be and lack of skills in systematic thinking and creative thinking makes some teachers unable to solve problems effectively. Competency 2: Good service. It was the intention and willingness to provide services and improve the system. Provide services with continuous efficiency to meet the needs of service recipients, Competency 3: Self-Development It was a study, research, seeking knowledge, following up, and exchanging knowledge of new academic and professional knowledge. There is knowledge creation and innovation for self-development and job development, Competency 4: Working as a team.

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It is a form of cooperation to help and support the plan to encourage co-workers, Competency 5: Ethics and Code of Ethics for the Teaching Profession Experts offered their opinions on the problems. 2. The quantitative results, there were 353 people responding to the questionnaire and it was found that the majority were male, 211 people, accounting for 59.80 percent. Age between 45 - 54 years, accounting 39.70 had a master's degree, accounting 49.00 percent. had a marital status, accounting 56.90 percent. The results of the analysis of the competency problems required for vocational teachers in the 21st century at vocational education institutions in the Upper Northeastern Region 1 are shown in Table

Table 1 Conditions and problems of competencies required for vocational teachers in the 21st century in vocational education institutions in the Upper Northeastern Region 1

capacity	Problem level			number
	$\bar{X}$	S.D	Interpret results	
Core competencies				
Competency 1 Focusing on results in work	4.34	0 .68	a lot	5
Competency 2: Good service	4.36	0 .68	a lot	4
Competency 3: Self-Development	4.38	0 .68	a lot	3
Competency 4: Working as a team	4.40	0 .64	a lot	2
Competency 5: Ethics and Code of Conduct for the Teaching Profession	4.47	0 .76	a lot	1
together	4.39	0 .69	a lot	
Competency according to work line				
Competency 1: Curriculum administration and learning management	4.382	0.738	a lot	1
Competency 2: Student development	4.325	0.706	a lot	5
Competency 3: Classroom management	4.350	0 .701	a lot	3
Competency 4: Synthetic analysis and research for student development	4.377	0 .662	a lot	2
Competency 5: Leadership	4.258	0.678	a lot	6
Competency 6: Building relationships and cooperation with communities for learning management	4.347	0.673	a lot	4
together	4.340	0 .693	a lot	

From the table, it was found that the mean and standard deviation of the results of the analysis of the problem of competency required for vocational teachers in the 21st century in the upper Northeastern Vocational Educational Institute 1. When considering each competency aspect, it was found that. 1.The main competency aspect was overall. At a high level, considering each aspect, it was found that, 1) ethics and code of conduct for the teaching profession, 2) teamwork, 3) good service, 4) self-development, and 5) focus on achievement in work, respectively, in terms of competency according to work line The overall picture is at a high level. Considering each aspect, it was found that, 1) curriculum administration and learning management, 2) synthetic analysis. and research for student development, 3) Classroom management, 4) Building relationships and cooperation with the community for learning management, 5 student development, and 6 leadership, respectively.

Phase 2 The determination of the strategy for developing the competency of vocational education teachers in the 21st century at Vocational Educational Institutions in the Upper Northeastern Region 1. consists of 6 strategies including Development Strategy 1: Developing vocational teachers to have ethics and professional ethics for teaching. Development Strategy 2: Developing vocational education teachers to be able to work as a team. Development Strategy 3: Developing vocational teachers to have continuous and effective self-development. Development Strategy 4: Developing vocational teachers to be able to manage curriculum and learning management. Development Strategy 5: Developing vocational education teachers to be able to analyze synthesize and research for student development Strategy 6: Developing vocational education teachers to be able to manage their classrooms effectively and Evaluation results: suitability and feasibility Strategy for developing the competency of vocational teachers in the 21st century at Vocational Educational Institutions in the Upper Northeastern Region 1 found that a total of 34 respondents were mostly male, 73.50 percent, aged between 45–54 years, accounting 64.70 percent. had master's degrees, accounting 82.40 percent had marital status, and the results of the evaluation of strategies for developing the competency of vocational teachers in the 21st century of the upper Northeastern Vocational Educational Institutions 1. It was found that the mean and standard deviation of the suitability and feasibility of the strategy were found to be at the highest level of suitability overall. As for the feasibility of the strategy It is at a high level when considering each strategic issue. at a high level.

VI. DISCUSSION

The researcher brought the findings for discussion. Details are as follows:

1. Results of the study on the problems and competencies required for vocational teachers in the 21st century in upper Northeastern Vocational Educational Institutions 1 Summary of the results of data analysis, problems and competencies necessary for Vocational Education Teachers in the 21st Century in Upper Northeastern Vocational Educational Institutions. Top 1 has 5 core competencies : 1) focusing on work results, 2) good service, 3) self-development, 4) teamwork, and 5) teacher ethics and code of conduct. and competencies in 6 operational areas , namely 1) curriculum management and learning management, 2) student development, 3) classroom management, 4) analysis, synthesis, and research for student development, 5) leadership, and 6) building relationships and cooperation with the community Consistent with Atithep 's research. Khai Phet : Development of professional teachers' competencies for learning management in the 21st century. The research results found that Professional teacher competencies Consisting of learning management and classroom management and research to develop learning. which is consistent with the results of this research (Atithep Khai Phet , 2019) It is also consistent with the research of Pornsak Sujaritrak. Chanita Pilachai , topic: Teacher competency development model to support education in the 4.0 era The research results found that Teacher competencies to support education in the 4.0 era are as follows: 1) morality and ethics, 2) community relations and participation , and 3) giving importance to learners (Pornsak Sujaritrak and Chanita Pilachai , 2020)

2. Results of the strategy for developing the competency of vocational teachers in the 21st century of vocational education institutions in the upper Northeastern Region 1. Summary of results: The strategy consists of 6 strategies: Development Strategy 1: Developing vocational teachers to have ethics and professional ethics for teaching. In line with the research of Phrakru Niruti Worasophon (Vachiramedhiworachat) Subject: Strategy for developing professional competency of teachers at Phra Pariyattitham School General Education Department, Area 4 The research results found that Strategies for developing teachers' professional competencies include developing teacher potential; Educational personnel to have morality Stable in the profession Development Strategy 2: Developing vocational education teachers to be able to work as a team. Development Strategy 3: Developing vocational teachers to have continuous and effective self-development.

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Development Strategy 4: Developing vocational education teachers to be able to manage the curriculum and learning management (Phrakhru Nirutiworasophon (Vachiramatee Worachat) , 2023) and consistent with the research of Tee Rapap Phetmalaikul. Subject: Academic administration model and learning management to enhance characteristics and skills in the 21st century in basic educational institutions. The research results found that Vocational education teachers should develop teaching and learning. and course work To enhance the characteristics and skills of 21st century learners, the highest level is to promote reading. Development Strategy 5: Developing vocational education teachers to be able to analyze and synthesize and research for student development and development strategy number 6: developing vocational teachers to be able to manage classrooms effectively (Tee Rapap Phetmalaikul , 2019)

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the current study, the author recommends the following measures, as presented below:

1. Recommendation for applying the research results

1) The research results at the problem Summary and recommendations from research on strategies for developing competency of vocational teachers in the 21st century of vocational education institutions in the upper Northeastern Region 1 found that the necessary competencies of vocational teachers in the 21st century of vocational education institutions Upper Northeastern Region 1 have 5 core competencies: 1) focusing on work results, 2) good service, 3) self-development, 4) teamwork, and 5) teacher ethics and code of conduct. and competencies in 6 operational areas, namely 1) curriculum management and learning management, 2) student development, 3) classroom management, 4) analysis, synthesis, and research for student development, 5) leadership, and 6) building relationships and cooperation with the community. Based on the research findings regarding the competencies of vocational teachers in the 21st century from vocational institutions in Upper Northeastern Region 1, the following recommendations for various organizations can be suggested: Ministry of Education (or Office of the Vocational Education Commission - OVEC): Should promote curriculum development and provide additional training to enhance teacher competencies in curriculum management and learning management, as well as in analysis, synthesis, and research for student development, to equip teachers with the ability to innovate effective teaching practices in the digital age. Provide resources and tools for classroom management and student development, such as online learning systems or virtual labs, to enhance the learning experience. Teacher and Educational Personnel Development Institutes: Should create long-term training programs focused on improving teachers' self-development competencies, particularly in modern technology skills and language proficiency, to ensure they can adapt to global changes. Develop training programs to foster skills in teamwork and ethics and professional conduct, so that teachers can model ethical behavior and standards for students. Vocational Institutions in Upper Northeastern Region 1: Establish a unit or team responsible for overseeing student development and building relationships and collaboration with the community, allowing teachers and students to engage in real-world community projects, such as internships or research beneficial to local areas. Encourage teachers to take on leadership roles by providing opportunities for them to engage in educational leadership, such as organizing academic events or representing the institution in external collaborations. Research and Development Agencies: Should promote research projects aimed at improving vocational teachers' competencies in areas such as service excellence and performance-oriented work by collecting data from various institutions to identify concrete ways to improve teachers' professional practices.

2) Strategies for developing vocational teacher competencies in the 21st century in upper northeastern vocational education institutions 1 Consisting of 6 strategies: Development Strategy 1: Developing vocational teachers to have ethics and professional ethics for teaching. Development Strategy 2: Developing vocational education teachers to be able to work as a team. Development Strategy 3: Developing vocational teachers to have continuous and effective self-development. Development Strategy 4: Developing vocational teachers to be able to manage curriculum and learning management. Development Strategy 5: Developing vocational education teachers to be able to analyze synthesize and research for student development and development strategy number 6: developing vocational teachers to be able to manage classrooms effectively

2. Recommendations for further research and development

From the results of this research, the following are suggestion:

Based on the research that established clear strategies for developing the competencies of vocational teachers in the 21st century, the next research project could focus on the following topics: Evaluating the Effectiveness of Competency Development Strategies for Vocational Teachers Investigate the outcomes and effectiveness of implementing the six strategies for developing vocational teachers. Identify which strategies have the highest impact and which ones face the most challenges in practice. Integrating Digital Technology in Vocational Teacher Competency Development Explore how the application of digital technology can enhance teacher competencies in various strategies, such as using AI for self-development or improving learning management. Developing Teamwork Skills in the Context of Online Teaching and Learning. Research how vocational teachers can develop teamwork skills in an online environment and what factors contribute to successful teamwork in an era of shifting teaching models. Enhancing Vocational Teachers' Research Skills for Student Development in the Digital Era. Study methods to improve teachers' research skills so they can apply data effectively in the development of students, especially in the context of digital learning. Blended Learning Classroom Management in Vocational Education Investigate approaches to managing blended learning environments, combining in-class and online learning, focusing on classroom management and teaching efficiency. Promoting Ethics and Professional Conduct in Vocational Teachers in a Changing Social Environment

Research how teachers can promote ethics and professional conduct amid rapidly changing social and economic conditions.

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